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Tree cavities and associated vertebrate fauna in a coniferous forest of Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir part of Pakistan

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Abstract: Tree cavities are a globally important structural element of forest ecosystems that host numerous cavity-dwelling vertebrates, but they have received little research in Pakistan. We investigated cavity-bearing trees, the attributes of their cavities, and their associated vertebrate fauna in a coniferous forest of Pakistan. We recorded 1140 trees in a 2-km² sampled area. We found 211 cavities (64% decay-formed and 36% excavated cavities) in 83 trees (41% live and 59% snags). Of the cavities found, 74% were recorded in trunks and 26% were in branches. Only 28% of the cavities showed signs of recent use by any vertebrate species. We observed 19 vertebrate species using cavities: 2 mammals, 13 birds (including 5 woodpecker species as primary excavators), and 4 reptiles. Height from the ground, entrance diameter, and depth of the cavities used by mammals were greater than those measurements of the cavities occupied by birds and reptiles. Our study shows that tree cavities have a critical role in providing nesting sites to many vertebrate species of Pakistan that require tree cavities in order to breed. We recommend such research be done in other forests of the country to investigate cavity availability and requirements of cavity users. We suggest that certain minimum populations of cavity-bearing trees should be maintained during silviculture practices to support populations of tree-dwelling vertebrates in the coniferous forests of Pakistan.

Key words: Tree hollows, cavity nests, wildlife, temperate pine forest, tropical pine forest, cavity-dwelling vertebrates

1. Introduction

Tree cavities are semienclosed structures, naturally formed or made by an excavator, in the trunk or branch of a living or dead tree. Generally, the formation of cavities in forest trees is attributed to fungal decay, insect attack, fire, or primary excavators such as woodpeckers (Mackowski, 1984; Inions et al., 1989; Hooge et al., 1999; Jackson and Jackson, 2004; Adkins, 2006). Many vertebrate species including small mammals, birds, and reptiles (Kitching, 1971; Hansell, 2005) require tree cavities for roosting, breeding, and protection from unfavourable weather and predators (Saunders et al., 1982; Mackowski, 1984; Newton, 1994; Nowak, 1999; Kunz and Lumsden, 2003).

The age and size of a tree have a primary role in defining the abundance and distribution of tree cavities. Older and larger trees possess more cavities than younger and smaller ones (Gibbons and Lindenmayer, 2002; Blakely et al., 2008; Koch et al., 2008). There is a close relationship between many species of cavity-dependent vertebrates and the abundance of large trees in Australian forests (Lindenmayer et al., 1991). Logging and deforestation reduce the abundance of tree cavities and their associated wildlife by altering the age structure

of a forest. Practically, large trees are targeted in selective logging and deforestation processes (Wardle, 1984), which reduces the roosting and nesting sites of obligate cavity-dwelling species (Mackowski, 1984; Lindenmayer et al., 1991). Despite their having high importance in providing foraging, nesting, roosting, and breeding sites, the information available about characteristics of the trees, their cavities, and associated wildlife species is insufficient, especially for tropical and high elevation regions (Marsden and Jones, 1997; Law and Andersen, 2000; Lumsden et al., 2002; Courtney and Debus, 2006; Murphy and Legge, 2007; Cornelius et al., 2008; Remm and Lohmus, 2011).

There are 3 zoogeographic regions (Oriental or Indo-Malayan, Palaearctic, and Ethiopian) that meet in the land mass of Pakistan, giving it wide geographic, altitudinal, and physiographic variations from the tropical coast in the south to the high mountains in the north, with altitudinal variation from sea level to about 8000 m. The mountainous areas provide substantial habitats for wildlife, mainly in the form of tropical deciduous forests and dry and moist temperate forests. The temperate forests are a global hot spot of bird diversity and host wildlife species of special concern, including endangered species (snow leopard,

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Panthera uncia, and woolly flying squirrel, *Eupetaurus cinereus*) and near-threatened species (common leopard, *Panthera pardus*). This ecology is home to 2 cavity-dwelling mammals (red giant flying squirrel, *Petaurista petaurista*, and long-fingered bat, *Myotis longipes*) and 13 cavity-nesting bird species, including woodpeckers (*Dendrocopos auriceps*, *Dendrocopos himalayensis*, *Picus squamatus*, *Hypopicus hyperythrus*), parakeets (*Psittacula cyanocephala*, *Psittacula himalayana*), owls (*Otus sunia*, *Glaucidium cuculoides*, *Otus spilocephalus*, *Glaucidium brodiei*, *Strix aluco*), great barbet (*Megalaima virens*), and the Himalayan cuckoo (*Cuculus saturatus*) (Roberts, 1991, 1992, 1997; Mirza, 2011).

Although tree cavities are a critical component of forest ecosystems worldwide and are well studied in temperate Europe, North America, and Australia (Goldingay, 2009; Remm and Lohmus, 2011), there is not much known about their characteristics and occupancy rates in Asia. Indeed, no report is available on such data from the wildlife ecologies of Pakistan and its associated territories. The purpose of this study is to 1) determine the abundance and characteristics of cavity-bearing trees, 2) describe the characteristics of tree cavities, and 3) determine the occupancy rates and cavity preferences of vertebrate species in a coniferous forest of the Azad Jammu and Kashmir territory of Pakistan. It is an initial step to fill the knowledge gap of tree cavities and cavity-nesting fauna in Pakistan, and to highlight the need for further research in this ecozone as well as all other forest ecologies of the country. This research is necessary to inform silviculture practices at local and national scales.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site

The study was undertaken in a 10-km² area that falls in the upper limit of the subtropical pine zone, mainly comprising deciduous mixed temperate–coniferous forest, located at Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, district Bagh of Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJ&K), Pakistan (34°51'N, 73°34'E; altitude range: 1066 to 2042 m; Figure 1). The climate of the district is subtropical highland, with a temperature range of 2 °C to 40 °C. Maximum and minimum temperatures are 40 °C and 22 °C in the hottest month (June), respectively, and 16 °C and 3 °C, respectively, in the coldest month (January). Average annual precipitation is 1500 mm (ERRA, 2007).

We divided the study area into 2 subsites: the first located at the upper elevation (2042 m) and the other at the lower elevation (1066 m). Each subsite consisted of a 2-km² area subdivided into 10 plots of equal size (i.e. 200 m²). From these, 5 randomly selected plots were visited for observations and data records. Subsite A (high altitude) was a moist temperate forest dominated by *Pinus wallichiana* and *Quercus incana* with glades of

mixed deciduous broad-leaved species. Subsite B (low altitude) was a subtropical pine forest dominated by *Pinus roxburghii*, *Quercus incana*, and *Olea ferruginea* mixed with deciduous species.

The study was carried out from September 2009 to August 2010, initially by conducting reconnaissance surveys of both subsites. We adopted a definition of 'cavity' as any excavated or decay-formed opening in a tree's bole or limbs having an entrance diameter and depth of more than 1 cm (following Blakely and Didham, 2008; Blakely et al., 2008). We surveyed all trees in the 10 sampling plots (5 plots of 200 m² at each subsite) for cavities. Depending on tree density, structure, and age, observations were made from the ground by unaided eyes, with binoculars, or by climbing the trees. The available cavities were observed for occupancy by any vertebrate species, wear of the cavity entrance, evidence of use (e.g., feather, hair, eggs, hatchlings, or juveniles), and direct sighting of the occupant species entering or exiting the cavity. We recorded the following parameters for each cavity-bearing tree and cavity: 1) tree species, 2) number of cavities in the tree, 3) state of tree (live or dead), 4) height of cavity entrance from ground, 5) location of the cavity (trunk or branch), 6) origin of the cavity (decay-formed or excavated), and 7) dimensions of the cavity (entrance diameter and interior depth). We estimated the entrance diameter of each tree cavity by taking the average of its horizontal and vertical (at right angles to one another) dimensions. Cavity depth was assessed by measuring from the lower lip of the entry to the base of the cavity.

2.2. Statistical analysis

The basic data were analysed using descriptive statistics. Mean values given in the text are mentioned with standard error (mean ± SE). We compared the cavity parameters (entrance diameter, depth, and height from ground) between dead and live trees by using the Student t-test and also tested for any difference among these 3 parameters of the cavities occupied by mammals, birds, and reptiles by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). We used the Pearson correlation to examine the relationship between cavity entrance diameter and cavity depth. We used Excel 2010 for data computation and Minitab 15 for statistical analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Tree composition and cavity-bearing trees

The survey of the 5 randomly selected sampling plots (200 m² each) at subsite A (temperate coniferous forest at the higher altitude) revealed that *Pinus wallichiana* and *Quercus incana* were the dominant canopy tree species comprising 74.7% and 16.8% of the tree populations, respectively. The rest of the 8 tree species (*Quercus dilatata*, *Melia azedarach*, *Morus alba*, *Prunus armeniaca*,

Legend **Map of Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, Azad Kashmir**

- City
- ★ Study Area
- ▬ Sanghar Bathara Forest
- ▬ Road

Scale: 1:30,000

Figure 1. Location map of the study site (Sanghar Bathara forest), Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan (courtesy of the Pakistan Wetlands Programme).

Bauhinia variegata, *Pinus roxburghii*, *Juglans regia*, and *Diospyros kaki*) contributed only 8.5% to the total tree population (Figure 2a). Of the 647 trees sampled from this 1-km² area, there were 34 (5.3%) cavity-bearing trees. The first 2 tree species (*Pinus wallichiana* and *Quercus incana*) constituted 91.5% of the tree population and provided 19 (55.9%) tree cavities, while the other 8 tree species (8.5% of the population) contained 15 (44.1%) cavities. *Pinus wallichiana* and *Quercus incana* contained more tree cavities in absolute numbers, but the other 8 species were more likely to form cavities, despite their low numbers. Irrespective of tree species, the overall estimated population of cavity-bearing trees was 3.4/ha and made up 5.3% of trees.

The survey results of the 5 sampling plots (200 m² each) of subsite B (subtropical coniferous forest at the lower altitude) are shown in Figure 2b. The total tree population of this 1-km² area was 493, among which *Pinus roxburghii* and *Olea ferruginea* were the dominant canopy tree species having proportions of 41.0% and 31.2%, respectively. The other 8 tree species (*Prunus armeniaca*, *Melia azedarach*, *Diospyros kaki*, *Quercus incana*, *Morus alba*, *Bauhinia variegata*, *Pyrus communis*, and *Juglans regia*) made up 27.8% of the tree population. Out of the 493 trees sampled, 49 (9.9%) contained cavities. Cavities occurred most frequently in *Olea ferruginea* (40.8%) followed by *Melia azedarach* (22.4%), while only 2%–6% of trees of the other 6 species contained cavities. *Pinus roxburghii* was the most prevalent tree (41.0%) of our study site, but contained only 1% of the cavities. At this site, the proportion of cavity-bearing trees was 10.0% with a density of 4.9/ha. Combined tree data of the 2 sampling sites revealed that 7.3% of trees contained cavities and the density of cavity-bearing trees was 4.5/ha.

3.2. Characteristics of cavity-bearing trees and tree cavities

The total tree population was higher at subsite A (647 trees) than at subsite B (493 trees), but the proportion of cavity-bearing trees was higher at subsite B (10.0% of trees) than at subsite A (5.3%). Between our 2 subsites, there were 12 tree species, of which 8 were common at both sites. *Pyrus communis* and *Olea ferruginea* were absent from subsite A and *Pinus wallichiana* and *Quercus dilatata* were absent from subsite B (Table 1).

In total, we recorded 211 cavities in 83 trees, with the highest average number of cavities per tree in *Olea ferruginea* (9.5%; all snags). The total proportions of dead and live trees were 70 (6.1%) and 1070 (93.9%), respectively. Of the cavity-bearing trees, 34 (41%) were alive and 49 (59%) were dead. We recorded 156 (74%) cavities in tree trunks and 55 (26%) cavities in branches. We recorded 136 (64%) cavities formed by decay and 75 (36%) formed by primary excavators. These combined data revealed that

Figure 2. Distribution of cavity-bearing trees at a) subsite A (dominated by temperate forest vegetation) and b) subsite B (dominated by subtropical pine forest vegetation) of study area at Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan.

the occurrence of the highest proportion of cavities was in *Melia azedarach*.

Of the total 211 cavities, vertebrate fauna occupied 60, with 53.3% of occupied cavities formed by decay and 46.7% built by primary excavators. All the decay-formed cavities were found in snags (59% of recorded cavities), whereas the majority (85.7%) of excavated cavities were recorded in live trees (41% of recorded cavities), with only 4 of them (14.3%) found in snags (Table 1).

3.3. Tree cavities and associated vertebrate fauna

The dimensions of tree cavities and their use by vertebrate fauna are given in Table 2. Occupancy of the cavities was determined by evidence of hair, scat, and feathers, along with direct observation of animals (where possible) inhabiting the cavities. We found 60 of the 211 cavities

Table 1. Characteristic of cavity-bearing trees, population, position, and types of tree cavities recorded at 2 study sites of coniferous mixed deciduous forest at Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan.

Tree species	State of the cavity bearing trees			Tree cavities (n)	Position of tree cavities		Nature of tree cavities	
	Live n(%)	Snag n(%)	Total n(%)		Trunk n(%)	Branches n(%)	Decay* n(%)	Excavated n(%)
<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	6 (50)	6 (50)	12	34	28 (82)	6 (18)	20 (59)	14 (41)
<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	3 (100)	0 (0)	3	4	4 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (100)
<i>Olea ferruginea</i>	0 (0)	20 (100)	20	60	42 (70)	18 (30)	58 (97)	2 (3)
<i>Quercus incana</i>	6 (60)	4 (40)	10	26	16 (62)	10 (38)	18 (69)	8 (31)
<i>Quercus dilatata</i>	2 (67)	1 (33)	3	8	5 (62)	3 (38)	2 (25)	6 (75)
<i>Melia azedarach</i>	9 (64)	5 (36)	14	32	26 (81)	6 (19)	7 (22)	25 (78)
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	1 (20)	4 (80)	5	11	6 (55)	5 (45)	7 (64)	4 (36)
<i>Morus alba</i>	2 (50)	2 (50)	4	11	9 (82)	2 (18)	7 (64)	4 (36)
<i>Diospyros kaki</i>	3 (100)	--	3	5	5 (100)	--	--	5 (100)
<i>Juglans regia</i>	--	1 (100)	1	3	2 (67)	1 (33)	3 (100)	--
<i>Pyrus communis</i>	2 (67)	1 (33)	3	8	6 (75)	2 (25)	5 (63)	3 (37)
<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	--	5 (100)	5	9	7 (70)	2 (22)	9 (100)	--
Total		34 (41)	49 (59)	83	211	156 (74)	55 (26)	136 (64)

*: Cavities formed by fungal attack, insect attack, wind fire, limb breakage, etc.

(28.4%) positive for the presence of any vertebrate species. Among them, 11 (18.3%) cavities were occupied by mammals, 41 (68.3%) by birds, and 8 (13.3%) by reptiles. Of the 19 vertebrate species we recorded, 2 were mammals, 13 were birds (7 of Passeriformes and 6 non-Passeriformes), and 4 reptiles (Table 2). Among the 60 cavities inhabited by the vertebrate fauna, 36 (60%) were located in snags. All 11 cavities occupied by mammals, 18 out of 41 cavities occupied by birds, and 7 out of 8 cavities occupied by reptiles were located in snags. Among birds, 4 of Passeriformes and 4 non-Passeriformes used cavities in snags. A golden-backed woodpecker (*Dinopium benghalense*) was observed occupying a cavity in an orchid tree (*Bauhinia variegata*).

The giant red flying squirrel (*Petaurista petaurista*) and the long-fingered bat (*Myotis longipes*) were the 2 mammalian species observed in the study area. Cavities used by the flying squirrel were at least 90 cm deep and their average height above ground was 9 m. In July 2010, we observed a giant red flying squirrel using multiple openings of a cavity traversing the entire height of a *Pinus wallichiana* tree. The cavities occupied by long-fingered bats (*Myotis longipes*) were found in dead *P. wallichiana* trees of about 77 years in age (estimated from the local forest record). Mammal cavities had entrance diameters ranging from 2 to 7 cm and were up to 20 m above ground level (Table 2).

In the present study, about 68% of the cavities were occupied by birds, including 7 species of Passeriformes

and 6 non-Passeriformes species. Among passerines, the most commonly observed species were the common myna (*Acridotheres tristis*) and the house sparrow (*Passer domesticus*). All 7 passerines used both decayed and excavated cavities. Although most of the nonpasserines were using their own excavated cavities in live trees, we observed a blue-throated barbet using a cavity excavated by a woodpecker. There were 41 cavities occupied by birds, of which 21 were inhabited by secondary cavity-nesters. The tree species with the highest number of cavities occupied by birds was *Melia azedarach* (10) followed by *Olea ferruginea* (7) (Table 3). The average entrance diameter of cavities occupied by birds was 5.6 ± 0.2 cm, average cavity depth was 42.5 ± 1.5 cm, and average height above ground was 5.9 ± 0.6 m (Figures 3a–3c).

We observed only 4 reptile species, 2 snakes and 2 lizards. The 2 snakes (Kashmir cliff racer, *Coluber rhodorachis*, and common cat snake, *Boiga trigonata*) used deep cavities (100 cm and 47 cm, respectively) in old dead trees. The 2 lizards (spotted barn gecko, *Hemidactylus brookii*, and Kumaon mountain lizard, *Japalura kumaonensis*) were found in cavities available in *Quercus incana*, *Bauhinia variegata*, *Prunus armeniaca*, and *Olea ferruginea* (Table 2).

For the vertebrates, mean cavity entrance diameter was 6.4 ± 2.8 cm, mean depth was 30.0 ± 12.0 cm, and mean height from the ground was 4.3 ± 0.6 m. The deepest cavity, used by a Kashmir cliff racer, was about 1 m deep. Cavity entrance diameter was positively correlated with

Table 2. Dimensions of tree cavities and their use by vertebrate fauna in a coniferous mixed deciduous forest at Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan.

Vertebrate fauna	Tree species	Approx. age (years)	Tree cavities (n)	Cavity entrance diameter (cm) avg. (range)	Height from ground (m) avg. (range)	Cavity depth (cm) avg. (range)
Mammals						
Flying squirrel	<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	80	4	14.3 (6–21)	9 (3.5–15)	>90* (>90)
(<i>Petaurista petaurista</i>)	<i>Quercus incana</i>	60	4	6.6 (3–8)	10 (7–12)	55 (35–85)
Long-fingered bat	<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	77	3	4.3 (2–7)	11 (3–20)	>90* (>90)
(<i>Myotis longipes</i>)						
Birds (Passeriformes)						
Common myna	<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	72	2	5 (3–7)	7 (3–11)	42.5 (35–50)
(<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>)	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	50	3	5 (4–7)	4 (2–5)	44 (40–46)
	<i>Diospyros kaki</i>	55	1	6 (6)	5.5 (5.5)	42 (42)
	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	77	1	5 (5)	3 (3)	47 (47)
Great tit	<i>Olea ferruginea</i>	72	2	5.5 (5.5)	3.5 (3.5)	30 (28–32)
(<i>Parus major</i>)	<i>Diospyros kaki</i>	45	1	4.5 (4.5)	6 (6)	30 (30)
Himalayan tree creeper	<i>Quercus incana</i>	54	2	5 (4–6)	10 (7–13)	37 (34–40)
(<i>Certhia himalayana</i>)						
House sparrow	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	85	3	5 (3–6)	3.3 (2–5)	45 (45)
(<i>Passer domesticus</i>)	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	63	1	6 (6)	4 (4)	65 (65)
	<i>Olea ferruginea</i>	87	3	6 (3–8)	3 (2–4)	45 (22–65)
Chestnut-bellied Nuthatch	<i>Quercus incana</i>	148	1	6 (6)	4 (4)	38 (38)
(<i>Sitta cinnamoventris</i>)						
Red-headed long-tailed tit	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	63	1	5 (5)	15 (15)	33 (33)
(<i>Aegithalos concinnus</i>)						
White-cheeked long-tailed tit	<i>Olea ferruginea</i>	93	2	4.5 (4.5)	3 (3)	36 (36)
(<i>Aegithalos leucogenys</i>)						
Birds (non-Passeriformes)						
Yellow-fronted woodpecker	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	36	2	6.5 (5–8)	4 (3–5)	43 (33–53)
(<i>Dendrocopos mahrattensis</i>)						
Himalayan pied woodpecker	<i>Quercus incana</i>	47	2	6 (5–7)	10 (8.5–12.5)	48 (45–51)
(<i>Dendrocopos himalayensis</i>)	<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	69	2	5 (4.5–5.5)	13 (10–16)	42 (39–45)
Scaly-bellied woodpecker	<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	62	2	6 (5–7)	13 (12–14)	42.5 (30–55)
(<i>Picus squamatus</i>)	<i>Quercus dilatata</i>	55	2	5.5 (4–7)	7 (5–9)	44 (40–48)
Rufous-bellied woodpecker	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	40	2	4.5 (3–6)	5 (4.5–5.5)	38 (32–44)
(<i>Dendrocopos hyperythrus</i>)						
Golden-backed woodpecker	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	98	1	7 (7)	3 (3)	30 (30)
(<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>)						
Blue-throated barbet	<i>Morus alba</i>	75	3	7.5 (6–9)	3 (3–3)	52 (42–60)
(<i>Megalaima asiatica</i>)	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	82	2	7 (6–8)	5 (4.5–5.5)	46 (43–49)
Reptiles (snakes)						
Kashmir cliff racer	<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	118	1	9 (9)	5 (5)	>100* (>100)
(<i>Coluber rhodorachis</i>)						
Common cat snake	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	145	1	5 (5)	3 (3)	47 (47)
(<i>Boiga trigonata</i>)	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	47	1	9 (9)	4 (4)	45 (45)
Reptiles (lizards)						
Spotted barn gecko	<i>Quercus incana</i>	97	1	5 (5)	3 (3–3)	32 (32)
(<i>Hemidactylus brookii</i>)	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	77	1	10 (10)	2 (2)	18 (18)
	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	68	1	7 (7)	3 (3)	6 (26)
Kumaon mountain lizard	<i>Olea ferruginea</i>	93	2	3 (3–3)	3 (2–4)	21 (18–24)

*: Given figures were used in computations ignoring the prefix symbols.

Table 3. Occupancy of tree cavities by vertebrate fauna in a coniferous mixed deciduous forest at Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan.

Tree species	Occupancy of tree cavities by vertebrate fauna					
	Cavities n	Mammals n (%)	Birds n (%)	Reptiles n (%)	Total used n (%)	Unused n (%)
<i>Pinus wallichiana</i>	34	7 (21)	6 (18)	1 (3)	14 (41)	20 (59)
<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	4	--	1 (25)	--	1 (25)	3 (75)
<i>Olea ferruginea</i>	60	--	7 (12)	2 (3)	9 (15)	51 (85)
<i>Quercus incana</i>	26	4 (11)	5 (18)	1 (4)	10 (38)	16 (62)
<i>Quercus dilatata</i>	8	--	2 (25)	-	2 (25)	6 (75)
<i>Melia azedarach</i>	32	--	10 (31)	1 (3)	11 (34)	21 (66)
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i>	11	--	3 (27)	1 (9)	4 (36)	7 (64)
<i>Morus alba</i>	11	--	3 (27)	--	3 (27)	8 (73)
<i>Diospyros kaki</i>	5	--	2 (40)	--	2 (40)	3 (60)
<i>Juglans regia</i>	3	--	--	--	--	3 (100)
<i>Pyrus communis</i>	8	--	1 (13)	1 (13)	2 (25)	6 (75)
<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	9	--	1 (11)	1 (11)	2 (22)	7 (78)
Total	211	11 (5.2)	41 (19.4)	8 (3.8)	60 (28.4)	151 (71.6)

depth ($R_{[df = 58]} = 0.51, P < 0.05$). The entrance diameters and depths of the cavities used by the mammals were significantly greater than those occupied by birds and reptiles (Figures 3a–3c).

Comparisons of tree cavity attributes related to their formation and to their occurrence in dead versus living trees are given in Figures 4a–4c and 5a–5c. There were no significant differences in entrance diameter or depth of excavated versus decayed cavities or in live versus dead trees.

4. Discussion

Numerous vertebrate species around the globe depend on tree cavities for their survival and reproduction. Although many studies are available on this ecological resource, it is only well documented and reviewed in Australia, Europe, and North America (Goldingay, 2009; Remm and Lohmus, 2011). Cockle et al. (2011) and Remm and Lohmus (2011) analysed biotic and abiotic factors contributing to the distribution, creation, and formation of tree cavities on the world scale. None of the studies referred to in these reviews originate from the 8 member countries (including Pakistan) of the Hindu-Kush Himalayan region, which cover ranges of tropical deciduous forests (Himalayan foothills) and moist and dry temperate Himalayan forests.

The meeting of 3 global zoogeographical regions (Oriental, Palaearctic, and Ethiopian) in Pakistan has gifted it with a unique variety of forest ecosystems, providing a home to 174 mammal species, 666 bird species, 195 reptile species, and 22 amphibian species. Many of them are cavity

users (Roberts, 1991, 1992, 1997; Khan, 2006). Despite such great wildlife diversity, the country does not possess a single report describing the characteristics of cavity-bearing trees, attributes of the cavities, or their associated vertebrate fauna in any of its forest ecosystems. Since the present study is the first formal piece of work exploring this unknown forest resource in Pakistan, we will discuss these results in context with similar studies conducted in other regions of the world.

It is difficult to compare studies conducted in different ecozones and zoogeographical regions because different tree species form cavities at different rates (Inions et al., 1989) and different animal species prefer certain tree species to others (Braithwaite, 1983; Taylor and Haseler, 1993). Tree-cavity abundance in any forest is likely to be strongly dependent on local climatic differences, forest stand age, disturbance history, cavity persistence, populations of primary excavators, and pathogen abundance (Cockle et al., 2011; Edworthy et al., 2012). Thus, the abundance and nature of tree cavities varies naturally to some degree between forest sites. Our study revealed a lower density of cavity-bearing trees at high latitude (temperate coniferous forest) and a relatively higher density of such trees at low latitude (subtropical coniferous forest). In contrast, Gibbs et al. (1993) recorded fewer snags and more cavity-nesters in tropical and subtropical forests than in temperate forests of North and South America. We presume to relate this difference to tree community composition and temperature at these 2 elevations, as the latter could facilitate the decay process in snags and the broken parts of living trees.

Figure 3. Comparison of a) cavity entrance diameter (cm), b) cavity entrance height from ground (m), and c) cavity depth (cm) of tree cavities used by vertebrate fauna in a coniferous forest of Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan. The box plots present the mean (×), median (horizontal line), 25th and 75th percentiles (box), and range (whiskers). a) $F_{(2,57)} = 4.72$, $P = 0.013$; b) $F_{(2,57)} = 7.31$, $P = 0.001$; c) $F_{(2,57)} = 23.64$, $P = 0.000$. Columns that do not share a letter are significantly different. Mammals (n) = 11. Birds (n) = 41. Reptiles (n) = 8.

The forests of both of our subsites had a dominance of coniferous trees, but we recorded proportionally more cavities in the less prevalent tree species. Likewise, Aitken and Martin (2004) recorded preferential selection by woodpeckers for aspen trees (a fast-growing deciduous tree) over the much more dominant coniferous trees in Canada, which was attributed to the susceptibility of aspen to heart rot fungus, facilitating the woodpeckers to excavate the core of the tree. The occurrence of proportionally more cavities in the less dominant nonconiferous tree species suggests a number of causes, i.e. density and hardness of tree wood; susceptibility to diseases and insect pests; size, age, spread, and intensity of canopy cover; fruit and seed source; preference of excavators; and secondary cavity-dwellers.

The population of 41.5 cavity-bearing trees/ha recorded in the current study is similar to the mean population of 40.1 ± 15.7 cavity-bearing trees/ha recorded in the wet and dry *Eucalyptus obliqua* forest of Tasmania, Australia (Koch et al., 2008). Our record of 110.5 cavities/ha (with an occupancy rate of 30 cavities/ha) matches the 111.7

cavities/ha recorded in an old growth tropical rain forest of Costa Rica (Boyle et al., 2008). Blakely et al. (2008) reported 963 tree cavities/ha in a southern temperate mixed beech forest of New Zealand. This was rated the maximum of 133 study sites reviewed by Remm and Lohmus (2011), who estimated the global median density of cavities to be 16/ha, with densities highest in Australasia and lowest in the Palearctic region. This comparison suggests that the tree cavity density of our study site is markedly higher than the global average density.

The majority of cavities in our sites were in dead trees (59%) versus living trees (41%), which supports the common perception that it is easier for excavators to create cavities in snags or that snags are more susceptible to decay-causing biotic and abiotic factors. Likewise, Harper et al. (2005) and Whitford (2002) recorded such preferential selection of dead trees in Australian forests. Conversely, Aitken and Martin (2007) and Boyle et al. (2008) found an 85% and 71% occurrence of tree cavities, respectively, in living trees of Canadian forests. Tree decay processes, wood hardness, the presence of excavators,

Figure 4. Comparison of a) cavity entrance diameter (cm), b) cavity entrance height from ground (m), and c) cavity depth (cm) between decay and excavated cavities occupied by vertebrate fauna in a coniferous forest of Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan. The box plots present the mean (x), median (horizontal line), 25th and 75th percentiles (box), and range (whiskers). a) $t = 1.54$, $P = 0.130$, $df = 58$, no significant difference; b) $t = 2.14$, $P = 0.037$, $df = 58$, significant difference; c) $t = 1.56$, $P = 0.124$, $df = 58$, no significant difference.

plant community, and rates of cavity decay are the factors considered to influence the proportion of cavities in living versus dead trees (Cockle et al., 2012; Edworthy et al., 2012). Of the total recorded cavities at our sites, 36% were excavated in live trees, of which 50% were done by 5 woodpecker species (*Picus mahrattensis*, *P. squamatus*, *Dendrocopos himalayensis*, *D. hyperythrus*, and *Dinopium benghalense*). This estimate is more than the average figure determined for the Eurasian region, where avian fauna excavate 26% of all tree cavities (Cockle et al., 2011).

Generally, it is believed that trees can actually provide more habitats for wildlife while dead than alive. Our data show that the majority (13 out of 19) of the recorded animal species were associated with snags, and apparently this is related to the higher occurrence (59%) of cavities in snags than in live trees. A similar relationship is evident from Australia where tree cavities frequently used by birds, bats, and squirrels were located in dead trees, as these were more likely to contain cavities (Beyer, 2008; Goldingay,

2009). Likewise, in temperate forests of North America, the majority of nest sites of cavity-nesting birds were found in dead trees (Scott et al., 1980; Raphael and White, 1984).

At our sites, 74% of the cavities were located in a tree trunk and 26% were in branches. Saunders et al. (1982) found similar results: 70% of cavities were in tree trunks and 30% were in branches in a plantation providing habitat to cockatoos (Psittaciformes) in Western Australia. Blakely and Didham (2008) reported an almost even distribution of the cavities in trunks (48%) and branches (52%) in a mixed broad-leaf-podocarp rainforest of New Zealand. Unlike these records, Whitford (2002) found the majority of cavities (86%) in tree branches in a eucalyptus plantation of Western Australia. Due to lack of sufficient data, our study is unable to explain any difference in rates of use between branches versus trunks, which may include the relationship of cavity location with climatic factors, species-specific behaviour toward cavity position, formation, and size or longevity of the cavities.

Figure 5. Comparison of a) cavity entrance diameter (cm), b) cavity entrance height from ground (m), and c) cavity depth (cm) between cavities located in dead and live trees occupied by vertebrate fauna in a coniferous forest of Sanghar Bathara, Dhirkot, AJ&K, Pakistan. The box plots present the mean (×), median (horizontal line), 25th and 75th percentiles (box), and range (whiskers). a) $t = 1.67$, $P = 0.100$, $df = 58$, nonsignificant difference; b) $t = 2.12$, $P = 0.038$, $df = 58$, significant difference; c) $t = 2.07$, $P = 0.043$, $df = 58$, significant difference.

The observed frequency of cavities (2.5 per tree) is comparable to the records of Whitford and Williams (2002), who found 2.4 cavities per tree in the eucalyptus plantation. Similarly, Whitford (2002) reported 3.26 cavities per tree in jarrah trees (*Eucalyptus marginata*) and 1.92 cavities per tree in marri trees (*Corymbia calophylla*). Mirza (2011) speculated that a snag in a moist temperate coniferous forest of Pakistan might possess 20 or more cavities made by woodpeckers.

We found 19 vertebrate species belonging to 3 major classes of vertebrates using tree cavities. Other studies found a range of 10 to 46 species using cavities in forests of Australia and Canada (Saunders et al., 1982; Gibbons et al., 2002; Whitford and Williams, 2002; Aitken and Martin, 2007; Koch, 2007). The current study and the literature are unable to provide an exact number of wildlife species as full-time or seasonal (breeding or overwintering) users of tree cavity, particularly in the fauna-rich subtropical and temperate pine forest regions of Pakistan. A longer and

wider-scale study on cavity-dependent fauna may discover more users and their dependency scale. Occupancy of only 28.4% of the available cavities has 2 possible explanations: either the cavities were in abundance (more than the requirement of existing fauna), or the majority of them were unsuitable to host the vertebrate species. A small proportion (5.5%) of available cavities were used by birds in beech forests of Spain (Camprodon et al., 2008) and 5.4% of cavities showed signs of use in eucalyptus forests of Tasmania (Koch et al., 2008), whereas Gibbons et al. (2002) recorded 43% occupancy of all observed hollows in temperate eucalyptus forests in south-eastern Australia. Saunders et al. (1982) found that more than half of the available cavities were not used by cockatoos in Western Australia because of bird behaviour, and that many of these cavities were not actually suitable or available to the fauna. However, the nonuse of available cavities needs further investigation to determine what characteristics make a cavity suitable for use by vertebrates (e.g., location

of the cavities with respect to sun and wind direction, tree canopy cover, population of prey and predator species, and relative locations of their nests).

Our study revealed that the reason cavity height above ground was significantly higher for excavated cavities than for decay-formed cavities relates to an assumption that excavators tend to prefer higher nest sites to avoid predation. The mean height of occupied cavities above ground (4.28 ± 0.55 m) was similar to that reported by Goldingay (2009), who found that more than 75% of 33 parrot species had cavity entrances within 5 m of the ground. A positive relationship found between cavity entrance diameter and cavity depth is supported by the findings of Blakely and Didham (2008), in which the cavity entrance size was strongly positively correlated with internal cavity volume in a mixed broad-leaf–podocarp rainforest of New Zealand.

Finally, this is the first systematic survey of the distribution and some structural characteristics of tree cavities in a forest located at an altitude representing a transition zone between tropical and temperate forest ecozones in the Azad Jammu and Kashmir territory associated with Pakistan. It provides an ideal framework for future research on how structural characteristics of trees and tree cavities, along with their spatial and temporal distribution, affect the wildlife species composition and community structure. Similar studies should be extended to all major forest ecologies of Pakistan because information on the availability and use of tree cavities is important for

conserving cavity-using fauna. This preliminary study helps us to understand the abundance of tree cavities in the forests of Pakistan, which matches those recorded in studies conducted in other countries, but further studies are needed to understand cavity availability on a large scale. The fact that not all cavities were occupied suggests that cavities may not be a limiting resource, but this needs further investigations on cavity attributes, cavity-bearing tree species, behaviours, and the needs of cavity-nesting species or a nest-box addition experiment.

In Pakistan, a selection silviculture system is generally practiced for regeneration of coniferous forests. Under this system, thinning among the smaller trees is carried out simultaneously with the removal of mature trees. The removal of all dead, dying, diseased, and defective trees is also recommended to maintain good sanitary conditions (Champion et al., 1965; Siddiqui, 1996). Contrary to this, our study suggests that the availability of snags has a significant role in providing tree cavities. Wardle (1984) proposed that the practice of selective logging targets the large trees, thus reducing nesting sites for cavity-dependent vertebrate fauna (Mackowski, 1984; Lindenmayer et al., 1991). These facts warrant comprehensive investigations to identify the impact(s) of the existing silviculture practices on all components of forest ecology, including cavity-dwelling vertebrate species, so that certain recommendations can be made to retain some population of old trees and snags.

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